

Unveiling the Potential of Hypergeometric Analysis for Enhanced Co-Infection Detection in SARS-CoV-2: Integrating ASV-like Inference for a Comprehensive Approach

Melany Calderón-Osorno¹[0000-0001-9835-2132]

Costa Rica National High Technology Center `mcalderono@cenat.ac.cr`

Abstract. The global impact of the COVID-19 pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2 is highlighted, with millions affected and deceased. The emergence of multiple variants led to the potential for co-infections, motivating investigations into bioinformatic strategies for understanding the complex landscape of simultaneous infections. Three bioinformatics pipelines were compared for co-infection detection. ASV calling through QIIME2 showed challenges, while ASV calling via R analysis exhibited low accuracy (3.4%). A hybrid approach integrating ASV inference with hypergeometric analysis improved co-infection detection (accuracy of 28%) compared to ASV alone. Integration of hypergeometric analysis enhanced co-infection detection, suggesting a promising avenue for future research to refine co-infection analysis strategies.

Keywords: Co-infection · ASV · Lineage.

1 Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, which emerged from the SARS-CoV-2 virus (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2), had a significant impact worldwide. By March 2023, an estimated 676 million people were affected by COVID-19, resulting in approximately 6 million reported deaths [1]. Throughout the course of the pandemic, numerous investigations arose around the COVID-19 disease. Researchers developed bioinformatic tools and pipelines that allowed them to better understand the infectious agent [2–12].

Over the course of the pandemic, a substantial number of SARS-CoV-2 variants circulated, with around 3300 Pango lineages documented as of August 2023 [13]. This diverse array of variants introduces the potential for multiple simultaneous infections (co-infections) with distinct virus strains, some of which may have gone unnoticed [14].

Various bioinformatics strategies have been proposed to investigate concomitant infections. These approaches encompassed (1) haplotype identification [15–17], (2) genome assembly coupled with hypergeometric distribution analysis [18], (3) genome assembly and (4) ASV (amplicon sequence variant) calling [14]. Molina-Mora et al. conducted a study comparing the efficacy of some

of these strategies in identifying co-infections. Their findings indicated that the metagenome assembly approach achieved an accuracy rate of 46.2% in identifying co-infections. In contrast, the strategy based on ASV-like inference demonstrated a significantly higher accuracy rate of 96.2% [14].

In our pursuit to evaluate the efficacy of the ASV-like strategy, we investigated samples that had been previously determined as co-infected using hypergeometric analysis. Notably, the ASV-like strategy did not exhibit superior effectiveness. In light of this, we integrate a hybrid approach that merges the ASV method with the precision of hypergeometric analysis.

2 Methods

2.1 Sample collections

We collected a total of 175 sequences positive for co-infections using the SRA toolkit (v3.0.1), extracted from Projects PRJNA716985 and PRJNA720050 accessible on NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). Raw sequences were downloaded and underwent processing on the Kabré supercomputer. These samples were obtained in the United States during the period from January to September 2021 and were sequenced using the Illumina platform. Co-infections within these samples were initially detected using a combination of genome assembly and hypergeometric distribution analysis [18].

2.2 ASV-like inference

For the detection of Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs) within each sample, we employed the QIIME2 software package (v2021.4) [19] with the DADA2 (Divisive Amplicon Denoising Algorithm 2) tool [20]. The standard protocol of this software implemented with a total execution time of 3 hours 5 minutes. For taxonomy classification, we employed the scikit-learn naive-Bayes classifier methodology, which is integrated within QIIME2. Initially, a lineage-specific classifier for SARS-CoV-2 was trained using a custom database (outlined below) through the RESCRIPt plugin. This was achieved by employing the feature-classifier fit-classifier-naive-bayes command. Subsequently, the ASVs were subjected to classification using the trained classifier. This process was executed using the classify-sklearn method within the q2-feature-classifier plugin, employing the default settings of the software with an execution time of 25 minutes. Additionally, the ASV sequences were exported and subjected to taxonomy assignment using the RDP Naive Bayesian Classifier algorithm, accomplished through the DADA2 package (v1.28.0) [20] within the R software. This step required a total of 15 minutes and was performed using R version 4.3.1.

2.3 ASV-like inference combined with hypergeometric analysis

For the hypergeometric analysis, mutations within each ASV sequence were annotated using Nextclade (v2.14.0) with an execution time of 8 minutes [21].

Subsequently, a homemade Python script (Python v3.10.12) was employed to implement a hypergeometric distribution-based approach for the detection of SARS-CoV-2 lineages, requiring 10 minutes to complete [18]. The formula used for calculating the hypergeometric p-value is as follows:

$$P(X = K) = \frac{\binom{K}{k} \cdot \binom{N-K}{n-k}}{\binom{N}{n}} \quad (1)$$

Here, N represents the total count of mutations in the mutation database, K signifies the number of mutations within a specific lineage, n denotes the count of mutations in the ASV sample, and k stands for the number of mutations that overlap between the lineage and the ASV. Following this assessment, the procedure records the optimal matching lineage along with its associated p-value for each ASV.

2.4 Custom SARS-CoV-2 database

An initial custom database was created, incorporating the 395 lineages that were examined in the research [18]. For each virus variant, we obtained SARS-CoV-2 genome sequence that encompassed all distinct mutations of the lineage by utilizing the lineage search function on GISAID. This process involved limiting the search to complete and high-covered genomes. In preparation for QIIME2 classifier training, we generated a fasta file with the following structure: ">ID" for sequence identification and associated taxonomy in the format "ID SARS-CoV-2; VOC_class-lineage".

However, when working with the R DADA2 package [20], the database format needed to resemble that of 16S-rRNA databases for amplicon-based metagenomics (16S-rRNA). Therefore, we adapted the sequence name format in the fasta file to include both the organism and subtype, expressed as ">SARS-CoV-2; VOC_class-lineage". For the hypergeometric analysis, a database was established, encompassing the lineages that were documented during the investigation period. The compilation of lineages, comprising approximately 3304 entries, was acquired from the Pangolin repository (<https://github.com/cov-lineages>). Subsequently, utilizing the Outbreak.info tool (v1.0.1) [22], the distinct set of mutations associated with each lineage was extracted from GISAID.

2.5 Assessment of the pipelines performance

To evaluate the effectiveness of the pipelines for co-infection detection, which encompass the ASV calling through R analysis, ASV calling via QIIME2 analysis, and ASV combined with hypergeometric distribution, we compared the predictions made by each approach with the expected genotype. We performed a Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) analysis using Python software. For the ASV calling (R analysis) and the ASV combined with hypergeometric distribution pipeline, we calculated the Area Under Curve (AUC) of the ROC curve and evaluated the overall accuracy of the predictions.

3 Results

To identify cases of COVID-19 with co-infections involving distinct SARS-CoV-2 variants, we employed three distinct pipelines. Initially, the ASV calling method through QIIME2 analysis encountered challenges in assigning lineage levels to any of the samples. It categorized all samples as SARS-CoV-2 without specifying any lineage assignment (Therefore, the analysis was not further pursued). The ASV calling approach using R analysis, which integrated ASVs generated via QIIME2 and utilized the R package DADA2 for taxonomy assignment, exhibited insufficient performance in accurately identifying the reported co-infections. This strategy displayed an accuracy of 3.4% (Fig. 1).

In light of this, a third metagenomic approach was introduced, integrating the ASV calling method via QIIME2 with taxonomy assignment through the hypergeometric distribution-based method. This adaptation led to an enhancement in the capability of identifying co-infections, resulting in an attainment of 28% accuracy. Moreover, the integration of taxonomic assignment with hypergeometric distribution analysis notably amplified the efficacy of co-infection assignment by approximately eightfold. However, both pipelines exhibited an AUC value below 0.05, which suggests that the co-infection assignment performance is comparable to random chance classification (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Comparative performance of two co-infection detection pipelines for SARS-CoV-2. Metrics for ASV inference: AUC = 0.02, Accuracy = 3.4%. ASV-like inference combined with hypergeometric analysis demonstrates enhanced co-infection identification, achieving AUC = 0.18 and accuracy = 28.0%.

Fig. 2. ASV-based identification revealed co-infections in which all lineages shared fewer than 10 mutations, while ASV + hypergeometric distribution analysis identified co-infections involving more than 10 shared mutations across the genomes.

4 Discussion

The limited information available on SARS-CoV-2 co-infection may largely arise from the inherent methodological challenges associated with identifying co-infections using genomic analysis. This intricate process necessitates rigorous quality standards to minimize the potential impact of factors such as laboratory cross-contamination, technical sequencing complications, bioinformatic anomalies, and sequencing noise [23]. In this study, we have provided an analysis of co-infection cases. Our investigation involved the examination of samples exhibiting two or three distinct genotypes. We employed a metagenomic approach that utilized ASV inference, along with an ASV method combined with hypergeometric distribution analysis.

The ASV approach was initially developed for identifying bacterial communities using 16S rRNA. ASVs partition a genome into distinct units, referred to as clusters of gene sequences that share complete identity with each other. Notably, in the context of bacteria, this approach has been observed to provide a more refined taxonomy level since they do not cluster sequences using a distance-based threshold, a distinction from other alternative clustering methods [24]. In a study that utilized ASV inference for the analysis of SARS-CoV-2 co-infections, a remarkable accuracy of 96.2% has been reported in the identification of simultaneous infections involving the Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta, and Omicron variants. The study revealed that the ASV strategy effectively detected instances of co-infections involving variants that exhibited fewer than 4 shared mutations between them [14].

Despite the research demonstrating high efficiency, it is essential to recognize that the study exclusively focused on the B.1.1.7, B.1.351, P.1, AY.113, and B.1.1.529 lineages, each representing a distinct variant [14]. However, when extending the analysis to encompass various lineages of these same variants, the strategy encountered a notable decrease in its overall efficiency (Fig. 1). The ASV method effectively identifies the B.1.1.7 lineage in cases of co-infection, while the

P.1 lineage was detected in all samples except one. When co-infections involved these two lineages, the strategy successfully achieved their identification (Supplementary Table 1). However, it’s important to highlight that this study did not investigate instances of co-infections with the B.1.351, AY.113, and B.1.1.529 lineages. The co-infecting variants under analysis exhibited a shared mutational profile of up to 29 mutations between them (Supplementary Fig. 1). Notably, co-infections that were accurately identified using the ASV strategy displayed a commonality of fewer than 10 mutations between them, in alignment with earlier observations (Fig. 2).

In response, we integrated hypergeometric distribution analysis with ASV-inference. This methodology, originally proposed by Zhou et al., involves comparing the mutations present within each sample with the feature variations (mutations) characteristic of all established SARS-CoV-2 lineages. For each lineage, a hypergeometric test was employed to compute the probability (P-value) of observing successes (mutations shared between the sample and lineage feature variations) under the "null hypothesis". This null hypothesis assumes the absence of any distinct connection to the lineage. Upon obtaining a sufficiently low computed P-value, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a robust correlation between the sample and the considered lineage. This approach facilitates the identification of potential candidate lineages [18].

The incorporation of hypergeometric distribution analysis resulted in a substantial enhancement in the efficiency of co-infection identification, achieving an approximately eightfold increase (Fig. 1). This novel approach enabled the recognition of cases where the variants shared more than 10 mutations in common. Specifically, among the identified co-infections, approximately 75% corresponded to variants with fewer than 10 mutations in common between them, while the remaining 25% represented variants that shared more than 10 mutations in common across the lineages (Fig. 2)

This finding suggests the potential integration of hypergeometric analysis into co-infection analysis strategies, indicating its capacity to enhance their overall performance. While current research primarily emphasizes the detection of co-infections through the bioinformatics approach of genome assembly and variant allele frequency [23, 25–27], there is a promising avenue for future studies to explore the integration of hypergeometric analysis.

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, this investigation delves into the landscape of SARS-CoV-2 co-infections, shedding light on the challenges and opportunities within the realm of bioinformatics analysis. Through methodological exploration, the study shows the potential of ASV-like inference and its integration with hypergeometric distribution analysis to enhance the identification of co-infections, especially in cases where variants share a greater number of mutations. The hybrid approach emerges as a promising strategy, offering improved accuracy in co-infection detection. As challenges persist, future studies can build upon these findings to

refine and expand co-infection detection strategies, ultimately advancing our understanding of the dynamics of COVID-19.

6 Data availability

The scripts and custom database utilized in this study are accessible at https://gitlab.com/CNCA_CeNAT/co-infections-biocarla-2023

References

1. Johns Hopkins University COVID-19 Dashboard, <https://coronavirus.jhu.edu/map.html>. Last accessed 14 Jul 2023.
2. Singer, J., Gifford, R., Cotten, M., Robertson, D.: CoV-GLUE: A Web Application for Tracking SARS-CoV-2 Genomic Variation. *Preprints.org* (2020). <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202007.0152.v1>
3. Chen, C., Nadeau, S., Yared, M., Voinov, P., Xie, N., Roemer, C., Stadler, T.: CoV-Spectrum: Analysis of globally shared SARS-CoV-2 data to identify and characterize new variants. *Bioinformatics* **38**(11), 1735–1737 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btab097>
4. Mercatelli, D., Triboli, L., Fornasari, E., Ray, F., Giorgi, F.M.: Coronapp: A web application to annotate and monitor SARS-CoV-2 mutations. *J. Med. Virol.* **93**(6), 3238–3245 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.26719>
5. Cecret. Available online: <https://github.com/UPHL-BioNGS/Cecret> (accessed on 28 June 2023).
6. Harshil, P., Sarai, V., Sara, M., Jose, E.-C., Michael, L.H., Gisela, G., nf-core bot, Phil, E., Miguel, J., Stephen, K., et al.: Nf-Core/Viralrecon. *Zenodo* (2021). <https://zenodo.org/record/7764938>
7. Connor-Lab: Ncov2019-Artic-Nf. *GitHub* (2022). <https://github.com/connor-lab/ncov2019-artic-nf>
8. Dezordi, F.Z., Neto, A.M.d.S., Campos, T.d.L., Jeronimo, P.M.C., Aksenon, C.F., Almeida, S.P., Wallau, G.L., Fiocruz COVID-19 Genomic Surveillance Network: ViralFlow: A Versatile Automated Workflow for SARS-CoV-2 Genome Assembly, Lineage Assignment, Mutations and Intrahost Variant Detection. *Viruses* **14**(2), 217 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/v14020217>
9. Truong Nguyen, P.T., Plyusnin, I., Sironen, T., Vapalahti, O., Kant, R., Smura, T.: HAVoC, a bioinformatic pipeline for reference-based consensus assembly and lineage assignment for SARS-CoV-2 sequences. *BMC Bioinformatics* **22**(1), 373 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-021-04289-7>
10. NCBI: SARS-CoV-2 Variant Calling (SC2VC) Pipeline. *GitHub* (2023). <https://github.com/ncbi/sars2variantcalling>
11. Tilloy, V., Cuzin, P., Leroi, L., Guérin, E., Durand, P., Alain, S.: ASPICov: An automated pipeline for identification of SARS-Cov2 nucleotidic variants. *PLoS ONE* **17**(1), e0262953 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0262953>
12. Bukur, T., Riesgo-Ferreiro, P., Sorn, P., Gudimella, R., Hausmann, J., Rösler, T., Löwer, M., Schrörs, B., Şahin, U.: CoVigator - a Knowledge Base for Navigating SARS-CoV-2 Genomic Variants. *Viruses* **15**(6), 1391 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/v15061391>

13. Cov-lineages Pango Lineages, <https://cov-lineages.org>. Last accessed 14 Jul 2023.
14. Molina-Mora, J.A., Cordero-Laurent, E., Calderón-Osorno, M. et al. Metagenomic pipeline for identifying co-infections among distinct SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern: study cases from Alpha to Omicron. *Sci Rep* 12, 9377 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-13113-4>
15. Young, B. E. et al. Effects of a major deletion in the SARS-CoV-2 genome on the severity of infection and the inflammatory response: An observational cohort study. *Lancet* **396**(10251), 603–611 (2020).
16. Hashim, H. O. et al. Infection with different strains of SARS-CoV-2 in patients with COVID-19. *Arch. Biol. Sci.* **72**(4), 575–585 (2020).
17. Liu, R. et al. Genomic epidemiology of SARS-CoV-2 in the UAE reveals novel virus mutation, patterns of co-infection and tissue specific host immune response. *Sci. Rep.* **11**(1), 1–14 (2021).
18. Zhou, H.-Y. et al. Genomic evidence for divergent co-infections of SARS-CoV-2 lineages. *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal* **20**, 4015–4024 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csbj.2022.07.042>
19. Bolyen, E. et al. Reproducible, interactive, scalable and extensible microbiome data science using QIIME 2. *Nature Biotechnology* 37: 852–857 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-019-0209-9>.
20. Benjamin, J. et al. Dada2: high-resolution sample inference from Illumina amplicon data. *Nature Methods*, 13(7):581, 2016. doi: 10.1038/nmeth.3869.
21. Aksamentov, I., Roemer, C., Hodcroft, E.B., Neher, R.A. Nextclade: clade assignment, mutation calling and quality control for viral genomes. *Journal of Open Source Software*, vol. 6, no. 67, p. 3773, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03773>.
22. Alkuzweny, M., Gangavarapu, K., Hughes, L. Outbreakinfo: outbreak.info R Client. Python package version 1.0.1, Mar. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/outbreak-info/python-outbreak-info>.
23. Peñas-Utrilla, D. et al. Systematic genomic analysis of SARS-CoV-2 co-infections throughout the pandemic and segregation of the strains involved. *Genome Med.* 2023 Jul 24;15(1):57. doi: 10.1186/s13073-023-01198-z. PMID: 37488638; PMCID: PMC10367318.
24. Schloss, P.D. Amplicon Sequence Variants Artificially Split Bacterial Genomes into Separate Clusters. *mSphere*. 2021 Aug 25;6(4):e0019121. doi: 10.1128/mSphere.00191-21. Epub 2021 Jul 21. PMID: 34287003; PMCID: PMC8386465.
25. Combes, P. et al. Evidence of co-infections during Delta and Omicron SARS-CoV-2 variants co-circulation through prospective screening and sequencing. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2022 Nov;28(11):1503.e5-1503.e8. doi: 10.1016/j.cmi.2022.06.030. Epub 2022 Jul 2. PMID: 35792280; PMCID: PMC9250411.
26. Bolze, A. et al. Evidence for SARS-CoV-2 Delta and Omicron co-infections and recombination. *Med.* 2022 Dec 9;3(12):848-859.e4. doi: 10.1016/j.medj.2022.10.002. Epub 2022 Oct 20. PMID: 36332633; PMCID: PMC9581791.
27. Rockett, R.J. et al. Co-infection with SARS-CoV-2 Omicron and Delta variants revealed by genomic surveillance. *Nat Commun.* 2022 May 18;13(1):2745. doi: 10.1038/s41467-022-30518-x. PMID: 35585202; PMCID: PMC9117272.